

Impact of the Secondary Heater Temperature on the Properties of Draw Textured Yarn and its Fabric

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Abstract:

Synthetic yarn especially draw textured yarn (DTY) is increasingly favored worldwide due to its advantages, availability, and ease of production over natural fibers. The bulk of DTY plays a critical role in determining fabric properties, influenced significantly by the secondary heater temperature during manufacturing. In this direction, trials were conducted on an AFT-1100-11DD machine using 240/48 SD, DD polyester POY. Six trials were conducted by varying the secondary heater temperature while maintaining other parameters constant. Yarn tensions and fabric appearances were evaluated across different settings. It was observed that, an increase in the secondary heater temperature led to a reduction in bulk, decreased boiling water shrinkage (BWS %), and caused variations in surface appearance. Power consumption also escalated with higher temperatures. Yarn properties like denier, tenacity, and elongation remained consistent across trials, mitigating the secondary heater's role in stabilizing these yarn properties post-primary heating. The inverse effect of secondary heater temperature crucially influences the bulk and fabric behavior of DTY, which is significant for applications in the weaving and knitting industries. Higher secondary heater temperatures decrease the bulk and increase the yarn stability, impacting fabric aesthetics and performance metrics like air permeability and drape coefficient.

Keywords: Air permeability, Bulk, Drape coefficient, Draw Textured Yarn, Secondary Heater Temperature

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1. Introduction

The whole world is going after the usage of polyester yarn in every aspect of life because of the limitations in the cotton growing fields. The properties of the draw textured yarn (DTY) especially its bulk, play a crucial role in determining the end use and the fabric behavior. The structure and design of heating elements i.e. primary heater and secondary heater have been the subject of scientific research for many years. The main function of the heating elements is to heat the yarn to the desired temperature. They should also ensure that a constant temperature level is maintained over a longer period. This is necessary so that the reorganization of intermolecular bonds can take place beyond the glass transition temperature T_g of the polymer, while it is important to stay below the melting point T_m so that the yarn does not break [1]. It is reviewed that as such there will be no impact on the properties like denier, tenacity, and elongation as on the changing of the secondary heater temperature [2]. There will be an impact on HCC% (Hot Crimp Contraction %), BWS% (Boiling Water Shrinkage %), and surface appearance depending on the difference in the secondary heater temperature. The power consumption also increases as the secondary heater temperature increases. Hence the work is carried out to determine the various fabric characteristics of the DTY.

The role of the primary heater (PH) is to mobilize the molecules and give the desired yarn properties with the help of the Draw ratio and D: Y ratio [1]. Drawing in the heaters can develop molecular orientation significantly [3]. Secondary heaters are 'non-contact' or convective type i.e. in tubular form with limited surface contact on the running textured yarn. The secondary heater makes the texturized yarn stable for

the subsequent process. Although the temperature of the secondary heater will be lower than the primary heater, but still morphological changes are expected to happen [4]. By increasing the secondary heater temperature, a significant reduction in the crimp value and residual torque of the yarn can be observed. It might be a physical phenomenon. The springiness or the flexibility of the yarn reduces with the increase of the secondary heater. It becomes stiffer. However, if the temperature of the secondary heater exceeds that of the primary heater, molecular reorientation will take place, and this can be observed through changes in the physical properties of the DTY.

Figure 1 - Texturized yarn with low & uniform bulk [5]

Figure 2 - Texturized yarn with high bulk [6]

The bulk of the DTY is formed after the twisting-untwisting zone which is desirable for the DTY. The quantity of the bulk is decided on the end uses. As the secondary heater temperature is increased, the yarn gets more shrink between the intermediate and output roller and hence the bulk becomes lesser. The secondary heater is to heat-set and stabilize the yarn surface [7]. Heat-setting is a heat treatment by which shape retention, crease resistance, resilience, and elasticity are imparted to the fibers. It also brings changes in strength, stretchability, softness, dyeability, and sometimes the color of the material [8].

2. Objective

In the Texturising Machine and that of the connecting Industries, there is no hard & fast rule in determining the temperature of the Primary and that of Secondary Heaters. It all decided by the Trial and error methods conducted by the departmental and that of QC Manager after knowing the end use of the DTY Products.

This experiment conducted in the floor level would be a great guidance for the Industrial workforce to know the impact of the Secondary heater setting vis-a vis yarn properties in a very comprehensive way. Hence this work is carried out to know the yarn properties in relation to secondary heater temperature. A higher difference in secondary heater temperature can also create the TKD (Tube knitting Dyeing) variation and there should not be much difference (not more than 20 degree Centigrade) in the same lot no.so far as the dyed fabric is concerned.

3. Materials and Methods

The conducted trial was arranged in AYM Syntex Limited, Silvassa who were kind enough to let us use the machine, POY spools, Manpower, and paper tubes. The available POY was 240/48 SD, DD (Bluish grey shade) CIR. The trials were conducted on three positions of the machine.

Table 1 - Texturizing machine specifications and its parameters

Machine Specifications	
Length of the Primary Heater	1750 mm
Secondary Heater	1450 mm
length of the cooling plate	1200 mm
Primary Heater tube Inner Diameter	7 mm
Secondary Heater tube Inner Diameter	4 mm
1-4-1 PU disc diameter	54 mm
1-4-1 PU disc thickness	9 mm
Machine Parameters	
Machine Speed	600 mpm
D:R ratio	1.73
D:Y ratio	1.90
Primary Heater Temperature	190°C

Secondary Heater Temperature	Varying
SOF	1.095
Take up	1.068
CPM	300
Spindle speed	3356 rpm
Oil roller speed	1.30 mpm

Table 2 - POY Properties

Denier	240.99
Elongation %	147.08
Tenacity	2.64 gpd
U%	1.18
DF	67.18
BWH	65.62
Nips/meter	4.5
Spin finish %	0.48

Table 3 - Experimental details regarding eater temperatures

Trial No.	PH Temperature	SH Temperature
1	190°C	150°C
2	190°C	165°C
3	190°C	180°C
4	190°C	200°C
5	190°C	210°C
6	190°C	80°C

Tensions were measured at positions 1, 2, and 3, with average values denoted as T_1 , T_2 , and T_3 respectively. For each trial, the values of T_1 , T_2 , T_3 , and the T_2/T_1 ratio were recorded and are listed in Table 4.

Table 3 - The average value of tensions in the yarn at three different machine positions with varying secondary heater temperature

Trial No.	Avg T_1	Avg T_2	Avg T_3	T_2/T_1
1	61.67	50.33	27.33	0.82
2	61.00	50.33	31.67	0.83
3	63.00	51.00	31.00	0.80
4	61.33	51.00	31.00	0.83
5	59.33	45.33	29.67	0.76
6	61.00	53.00	24.33	0.87

From Table 4, it can be observed that there is no significant difference in T_1 , T_2 , and T_2/T_1 ratio as these phenomena occur before the secondary heater. The T_3 value was found to be lowest in 80°C as the yarn becomes slack after the delivery roller. It is to be noted that the take-up speed was adjusted to maintain the package hardness in accordance with the other parameters.

For the reference, please the sketch drawn of a Texturisation machine

Sketch of a texturing machine where the location of the T1, T2 and T3 are shown

4. Results and Discussion

All six sample packages were tested in AYM Syntex Limited's Laboratory, Silvassa and the results are displayed in Table 5.

Table 4 - The average values of draw textured yarn properties at various secondary heater temperatures

Trial No.	PH/SH Temp (°C)	Avg Denier	Avg Tenacity (gm/denier)	Avg Elongation %	BWS%	HCC%	Snarling (number of snarls/meter)	Bulk (cm ³ /gm)
1	190/150	151.5	4.19	24.63	2.75	34.22	44	63.21
2	190/165	150.4	4.24	24.19	2.77	34.18	45	65.10
3	190/180	152.3	4.17	25.36	2.49	34.08	41	51.90
4	190/200	150.7	4.22	25.47	1.6	32.45	34	50.48
5	190/210	152.4	4.13	25.5	1.46	29.06	29	44.21
6	190/80	149.9	4.4	25.19	3.05	51.35	64	92.97

Figure 3 - Variation of DTY properties as a function of secondary heater temperature

The analysis of variation of the properties as a function of secondary heater temperature reveals several key trends. From Table 5 as well as from Figure 3, it can be observed that there are no significant differences in denier, tenacity, or elongation among the six samples. As the secondary heater temperature increases, tenacity shows a general decrease, with the highest tenacity observed at the lowest temperature and the lowest tenacity at the highest temperature, indicating a downward trend. BWS% also decreases with higher temperatures, suggesting reduced shrinkage. This relationship can be attributed to the fact that an increase in the secondary heater temperature leads to a reduction in the helix structure of the samples [9]. Consequently, with a reduced helix structure, the extent of BWS% also diminishes. Similarly, HCC% follows a decreasing trend, indicating less crimp contraction at higher secondary heater temperatures. Additionally, the number of snarls per meter decreases as the secondary heater temperature rises, indicating increased dimensional stability of the yarn, or formation of a more "set" yarn. Bulk shows a decreasing trend, indicating a more compact material at higher temperatures. This reduction in bulk is attributed to the heat-setting process, which causes the yarn to undergo thermal shrinkage, thereby lowering its bulk.

4.1 Hose Knitting

Hose knitted samples were prepared by using the DTY samples to evaluate their comparative characteristics, including appearance, bulk variations, dye uptake, and the presence of defects such as tight spots and broken filaments. This process is crucial for categorizing DTY packages and determining their appropriate grade. It serves as an essential parameter for assessing the quality and uniformity of DTY products. Typically, around 40 meters of yarn from each DTY package is knitted using a hose knitting machine. A flat wooden plate is then inserted into the knitted hose to ensure proper surface tension, which is essential for achieving a clear and accurate appearance. Comparative analyses are conducted based on these observations. The accompanying images depict the hose knitting of all six samples.

Figure 4 - Hose knitted fabric

It should be noted that the above hose-knitted samples were created from the samples of the DTY and were given the sample numbers with respect to the sample numbers of the DTY in accordance with their secondary heater temperatures. From Figure 4, it can be observed that Sample 5 appears slightly lighter compared to Sample 1, while Sample 6 appears darker. The darker appearance of Sample 6 is attributed to its higher volumetric structure, which contributes to a greater light absorption, hence a darker visual impression. It is a physical phenomenon. Additionally, Samples 4 and Sample 5 appear lighter than Samples 1, 2, and 3, which can be explained by the fact that the secondary heater temperature is higher as compared to the primary heater temperature in Samples 4 and Sample 5. The elevated SH temperature leads to a molecular reorientation in the yarn, affecting its appearance and resulting in a lighter color.

4.2 Woven Fabric analysis

A Sulzer double-width loom (40 inches + 40 inches) was used to prepare the plain-woven samples with the following specifications: Speed- 250 rpm. Reed: 52/2, Picks/inch: 56. A polyester double yarn of 40 Ne/65 D was used as warp yarn with 60 Ends/inch. The DTY samples were used as weft for the preparation of all six plain-woven samples. These woven samples were then tested for air permeability and drapability of the fabric. After doffing the cloth from the loom, the width of all woven samples was checked on the checking table and was found in the range of 38.9 – 39.2 inches. No significant difference was observed among the widths of the grey fabric.

Figure 5 - Impact of Secondary Heater Temperature on (a) Air Permeability and (b) Drapability Coefficient of the Fabric incorporating DTY as a Weft

4.3 Air Permeability

Figure – 5 (a) illustrates that the air permeability in the yarn decreases as the secondary heater temperature increases. The result at a secondary heater temperature of 200°C shows some deviation, which may be due to experimental error.

4.4 Drapability Coefficient

The Cusick Drapability Tester was used to measure the three-dimensional drapability of fabric under the influence of gravity. The procedure involved suspending a fabric specimen with a 15 cm radius over a supporting disc of a 9 cm radius. A parallel light source within the drapability tester projected the shadow of the draped specimen onto a piece of paper. This shadow pattern was then traced, and the drapability coefficient was calculated based on the traced pattern and formula.

Table 5 - Average Drape coefficient values at various Secondary Heater Temperatures

Woven Sample No.	area of large disk (W_0)	area of small disk (W_1)	Projected area of the sample (W_s)				Drape Coefficient = $(W_s - W_1)/(W_0 - W_1)$
			Observation 1	Observation 2	Observation 3	Mean	
1	490.6	122.65	364.40	365.1	364.8	364.767	0.658015129
2	490.6	122.65	370.64	371.23	369.89	370.587	0.673832495
3	490.6	122.65	397.71	398.22	396.51	397.480	0.746922136
4	490.6	122.65	343.57	342.65	344.12	343.447	0.600072474
5	490.6	122.65	372.73	373.96	374.12	373.603	0.682031073
6	490.6	122.65	333.16	335.23	332.58	333.657	0.573465598

Figure 5 (b) and Table 6 illustrate that, generally, an increase in secondary heater temperature corresponds to a higher drape coefficient. However, the sample at 200°C exhibits a lower drape coefficient than expected, although it is higher than that at 80°C.

5. Conclusion

The secondary heater in a texturizing machine plays a crucial role in determining the bulk variation of yarn, which is vital for its end use. As the secondary heater temperature increases, the bulk of the yarn decreases. If the temperature of the secondary heater exceeds that of the primary heater, molecular reorientation occurs, resulting in variation in dye uptake. However, physical properties such as denier, tenacity, and elongation are not affected by the secondary heater temperature. As the secondary heater temperature increases, the air permeability of the fabric incorporating DTY as a weft decreases. Higher secondary heater temperatures also lead to a higher drape coefficient, indicating that the fabric is becoming stiffer and exhibits poorer drapability. For applications requiring high strength and volume, lower secondary heater temperatures (e.g., 80°C) are preferable as they provide higher tenacity and bulk. For applications requiring dimensional stability, higher secondary heater temperatures (e.g., 200-210°C) are suitable as they result in lower BWS%, HCC%, and snarling. All parameters (BWS%, HCC%, number of snarls, and bulk) show a clear decreasing trend with increasing secondary heater temperature, indicating that higher temperatures lead to a more compact, less shrinkable, and less snarled material. In conclusion, the secondary heater temperature significantly influences the bulk and other characteristics of the yarn, underscoring its importance in the texturizing process.

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